

Social Support Behavior of School Heads and Work Place Spirituality as Predictors of Teacher Sense of Efficacy

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Abstract:- This study revealed teachers' metacognitive perceptions, quality of social supportive behaviors, and mental workplaces in the Caraga district. This study is a quantitative non-experimental study using a descriptive correlation study design with a sample of 300 teachers. Researchers used a set of customized survey questionnaires to obtain data from respondents who underwent content validity and reliability analyses. Data were analyzed using mean, Pearson's r, and multiple regression analysis. Overall results indicated that levels of social support behavior, workplace mental engagement, and sense of teacher effectiveness were evident in most cases. Furthermore, this study demonstrated that social supportive behaviors and psychological aspects at work had a significant impact on teachers' sense of accomplishment in the Caraga district.

Keywords:- Social support behavior, work place spirituality, teacher sense of efficacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers who question their abilities avoid difficult tasks they perceive as personal threats. They have low ambition and weak commitment to the goals they pursue. When faced with a difficult task, they tend to focus on their shortcomings, the obstacles they encounter, and all kinds of negative consequences, rather than on how to succeed. They do not put in the effort and give up quickly when faced with difficulties. After a failure or setback, the effects only slowly regenerate. They see poor grades as a lack of aptitude, so they don't lose faith in their abilities even after making a big mistake. They are prone to become victims of stress and depression (Saras Rodriguez, Lara & Martinez, 2021).

Teacher self-efficacy is receiving increasing attention in school psychology research because it influences classroom effectiveness, classroom performance, and student academic performance (Goddard, Bailes, & Kim, 2021). High teaching effectiveness leads to increased implementation of new teaching practices, increased motivation to work with students and teachers, and increased willingness to improve one's teaching skills (Pintus, Bertolini, Scipione & Antonietti, 2021).

Like many other professionals, teachers need to feel supported in their efforts. Regardless of profession, perceived high levels of support create more effective emotions and make individuals more likely to stay true to their careers. Unfortunately, the educational setting has not embraced the corporate world philosophy regarding the onboarding practices of new and junior employees and the

allocation of resources for human capital development. "No other profession accepts newly accredited graduates, puts them in the same situation as veterans, and offers institutional support (Hamm, Lambert, Little, Farmer & Harris, 2021).

It is on the above premise that the researcher investigated and explored the influence and effect of the variables which are social support behavior and work place spirituality on teacher sense of efficacy. It motivated the researcher to conduct this study since the new knowledge that can be generated from the results would be very helpful and beneficial to the students, teachers, parents, administrators and most especially to the Department of Education which also aimed to increase literacy with their program, Education for All, and finally, to improve the quality of education.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Social Support Behavior

Effective school leaders are usually teachers who lead teachers in schools. They know what teachers do and how to support them in class, but often support media professionals as class teacher collaborators when students are teaching together. I don't know how to do it. Unfortunately, most school leaders have little or no understanding of the role of media professionals in the educational process. A Missouri study that examined principals' perceptions of media professionals and their role in school libraries found that principals did not strongly endorse media professionals as teachers. It is important that school leaders understand the role of media professionals in the educational process and support student learning (Labrague, 2021).

Social support is an expansive construct that describes the physical and emotional comfort given to individuals by their family, friends, and other significant persons in their lives. Social support is purported to have a beneficial effect on health and well-being of people, and while it is a term that does not have a widely agreed upon definition in the adolescent health and development literature, it can be generally defined as the degree to which a person's basic needs are gratified through interaction with others. The social support construct encompasses a variety of specific characteristics of an individual's social world that might promote well-being and/or increase resistance to health problems (Lin, & Kishore, 2021).

Likewise, researchers have begun to illustrate how positive perceptions of teacher support can promote mental wellness, such that greater perceptions of teacher support are associated with higher levels of life satisfaction (Li, Yao, &

Liu, 2021) and subjective well-being (Matvienko-Sikar, Pope, Cremin, Carr, Leitao, Olander, & Meaney, 2021). Moreover, supportive teacher student relationships help maintain students' interests in academic and social pursuits, which in turn lead to better grades and more positive peer relationships (Wentzel, Muenks, McNeish, & Russell, 2018). In particular, research shows that you don't actually need social support to achieve positive results. Often the mere impression of receiving support is enough. For example, the perception that social support is available appears to reduce the negative effects of stressful events and hasten recovery, even when social support is not actually identified or used. In other words, even if adolescents do not seek support, simply believing that they will be supported positively affects their developmental success (Hwang, Yoo, Kim, 2021).

The first domain is on emotional. The more difficult to qualify parts of it is to what degree people's emotions should be included into the harm principle. It involves acting as a confidant for someone as such teacher might offer emotional support to someone by listening and offering sympathy after they've had bad news. Unfortunately this gives way pretty easily under any sort of scrutiny, not too long ago the idea of interracial marriage offended people, and even today the idea of homosexual relations still offends many people (Meshi, & Ellithorpe, 2021).

The second domain is on instrumental. Actions are directed toward goals only when the consequences are desired, allowing for contingencies between actions and consequences. Based on the second condition, we used an outcome re-evaluation operation to distinguish between the two behavioral control systems. Reappraisal-sensitive behaviors are said to be goal-oriented. But even if the outcome of the means, such as feeding a satiated animal, is no longer a worthy goal, but persists, the behavior must not be goal-oriented (Yang 2021).

Instrumental assistance is providing help or assistance in tangible and/or physical ways, such as giving money to someone who has lost their job or helping a bedridden person prepare dinner. Both emotional and instrumental support are important (Zhang, Huang, Zhang, Li, & Zhang, 2021).

A third area is under consideration. Employee engagement has emerged as a potentially important issue in employee performance and organizational management. There is growing evidence that there is a link between employee workplace engagement and hotel organization performance, even on an outcome basis. Practitioners and researchers tout engagement as an important factor related to work, but little is understood how to define and measure workplace engagement, particularly employee engagement in the hospitality and beverage industries (Liu, Wang, and Wu, 2021).

Rating inflation in performance appraisal is pervasive in organizations. Although most research on the sources of rating inflation and other biases in performance appraisal has examined cognitive processes (e.g. raters' use of heuristics; during recent years researchers have begun to document the

important role played by motivational factors as well Jolly, Kong, & Kim, 2021).

Global social support and positive life events in predicting Adaptive, externalizing and internalizing behavior. Gender differences were also observed. There was support for both main effects and moderator models of the association between life events and global social support. Positive ratings for life events appear to offset declining levels of social support worldwide. Gratitude has been discussed as a potential protective factor against maladaptation after exposure to major life events (Won, Choi, Ko, E., Um, & Choi, 2021). The variability in stressor ratings was assessed at the individual level, although stressor ratings may vary between occupations and even between individuals. Since the occupations are not constant, the types of tasks will vary depending on the participants. Therefore, it was not possible to determine whether differences in ratings at the individual level were actually due to differences in occupation. Testing individual occupations provides a more consistent basis for assessing individual assessments (Mitchell, Banyard, Goodman, Strøm, & Ybarra, 2021).

Beneficial. Teachers and school counselors are also important sources of information and support for young people entering high school and beyond. Although the positive effects of warm personal relationships with teachers have been the focus of much research, the role of teachers in shaping adolescents' feelings about their current school experiences and their future educational and career aspirations. There has been little focus on the effectiveness of information support (Zheng, Wang, Chen) & Xie, 2021).

Expectations and beliefs about students often influence the informational support teachers provide. Teacher expectations have the power to create social realities, as Jussim and his colleagues suggest (Felix, de Lourdes, Ribeiro, Cunha, Ramalho, Vaz & Conceição, 2021). (preliminary study on the psychosocial effects of Teachers rely on stereotypes to foster expectations of prejudiced groups of students. Prejudices and low expectations of these students may discourage teachers from taking courses that may improve their future educational opportunities (Exner-Cortens, Wright, A., Claussen, & Toratt, 2021).

As a result, teachers who place low expectations on poor minority students not only withhold moral support from those students, but also withhold informational support from them through inappropriate advice. increase. Students were not informed about the availability of college scholarships to apply for or opportunities at local universities and businesses. These students received little informational support from high school teachers and counselors (Ye, Huang, & Liu, 2021).

Schools, especially teachers, can therefore act as gatekeepers, preventing some students from progressing and encouraging others to progress. These young people receive little or no informational support from their teachers or parents, so they are unaware of how schooling will affect their future lives or what their future educational or career goals are. may have little understanding of what can be

achieved in Schools that do not help students connect their present life with their future are likely to have lower aspirations and expectations of education and be more skeptical about the benefits of schooling (Moore, Wierenga, Prince, Gillani, & Mintz, 2021).

B. Work Place Spiritually

Spirituality at work knows how to live with generalized Diversity from ideas to feelings. Only with spiritual maturity do we have the opportunity to replace the comfort of being with reason, massage postures, and a sense of the priorities of function and organization. The pursuit of sane ownership has caused conflict throughout the company's history and is still responsible for the loss of many talents today. Spirituality in the workplace is also about using our senses, enabling more careful observation, and respecting boundaries. This requires having feelings without any prejudice, but also without any prejudice (Sharma & Kumra, 2020). Transformation starts in the workplace when companies actively engage in developing the spirituality of their employees. This means treating employees as whole people in terms of their physical, mental, emotional and spiritual needs (Otaye-Ebede, Shaffakat & Foster, 2020). Promoting everyone at work shouldn't be viewed solely as an act of altruism. Research has shown that by engaging with the spiritual aspects of the human experience, organizations can help reduce stress, increase creativity, and enhance problem-solving (Garg, 2020).

Today, people are becoming more and more concerned about spirituality in the workplace. Spirituality is a movement aimed at improving working conditions. In this context, the aim is to encourage reflection on the topic of spirituality in the workplace. Research points to a significant positive impact of spirituality on the organizational structure of workforce and performance in the workplace (Rathee & Rajain, 2020).

The spirituality of people and teachers evolves over time and is influenced by meaningful relationships with others through lived experience (Zhang, S2020). When the concept of spirituality is discussed in the school context, there are different ways of interpreting it at the individual and group-centered faith-based levels, followed by secular concerns in schools (Arokiasamy, & Tat, 2020). Because it not only improves personal growth, enthusiasm and personal commitment in individual and team work, but also improves employee motivation, communication and quality of life. People with high spirituality are more receptive, so they get closer to work groups. Developing effective teamwork can therefore give you more control, which helps improve customer relationships (Paul, Jena, & Sahoo, 2020).

The first area concerns compassion. Compassion is a typical human emotion, characterized by pity and empathy for the grief of others. Compassion provokes a willingness to help others through their problems through comfort and emotional support. A compassionate person is one who understands the emotional state of another, sympathizes with it, and hopes that its suffering can be overcome or alleviated. For example, empathy can be understood as compassion when we feel sadness at the sight of others' misery or

misfortune (De Carlo, Dal Corso, Carluccio, Colledani, & Falco, 2020). In addition, compassion is described as an essential emotion to maintain peace for mankind and is the basis of the teachings and beliefs of various religions such as Buddhism, Catholicism, and Spiritualism, among others. Compassion is the ability to understand the suffering of others and responds to the desire to reduce and alleviate that suffering. The concept of compassion is both simpler and more powerful than empathy. This emotion drives us to want to help others and alleviate their suffering (Iqbal, Adawiyah, Suroso, Wihuda, 2020).

The second area is mindfulness. This has to do with the job itself and the content of the job and includes:

Personal interesting and meaningful work, sense of success and opportunities to utilize skills and abilities, opportunities for advancement, variety of tasks, responsibilities, autonomy in decision-making, lack of role clarity and role conflict, positive performance Evaluate work balance, harmony and interpersonal integration, lack of physical fatigue and monotony. For knowledge to be meaningful in work processes, a basic conceptual picture of workers is necessary (Lata & Chaudhary, 2020).

It is the role of previous learning and knowledge that is decisive in learning something new. This conceptual foundation is organized into structures composed of fields (facts, concepts, ideas, integrators) and operational or procedural knowledge (methods, strategies, spiritual knowledge) specific to each individual (Bharadwaj & Jamal, 2020).

The practice of mindfulness meditation is a common activity in many organizations. Indeed, in 2008 the Thai government announced a rule allowing government employees to take at least 30 days and up to 3 months of paid leave to practice meditation (Bantha & Nayak, 2020). Underlying this regulation is the fact that the Ministry of Social Development and Human Security believes that the practice of meditation not only contributes to the well-being of employees, but also has a positive impact on their work, which in turn contributes to the success of organizations. The assumption is that we believe it will lead to positive outcomes (Aboobaker, Edward & KA, 2020).

The third domain is about meaningful work. A sense of spirituality, psychological well-being and meaningful living at work are very important factors for an individual's physical and mental development and performance at work. For example, communal spirituality in the workplace can be defined as the recognition that employees nurture meaningful work done within a community context and have an inner life that is nurtured by it (Adnan, Bhatti & Farooq, 2020).

In addition, the feeling that they are doing meaningful work means that employees see their jobs, their jobs, as important, so they are much more likely to learn the necessary skills and develop a greater sense of responsibility. make it easier (Zou, Houghton & Li, 2020).). As noted by Dubey, Pathak & Sahu (2020), feeling that their work is meaningful encourages employees to work harder, strive for higher levels of achievement, and improve their job

performance. A sense of contentment, that is, a sense of self-satisfaction with mental health, is even greater.

C. *Teacher Sense of Efficacy*

Quality of work life is a process by which interest groups in Teacher effectiveness is the belief that teachers can adequately and effectively achieve specific goals. It exists in many areas of human functioning, including professional and personal behavior. Specifically, in the context of education, teacher effectiveness is the teacher's belief in his or her ability to plan lessons and achieve instructional goals. In fact, it is because teachers believe in their ability to teach students efficiently and effectively (Ormrod, 2006).

A teacher's organizational skills can have a positive impact on student educational outcomes. Teacher effectiveness is a teacher's belief in his or her personal ability to influence student performance and motivation. Active teacher participation helps teachers share common goals and fosters shared beliefs about the direction of their work and their ability to make a difference with their students (Durban & Catalan, 2012; Magno & Sembrano, 2007; Hallak, 2000).

The first domain of teacher efficacy is on student engagement. Teacher should challenge and engage students on learning outcomes. They should provide strategies that encourage student to connect what they are learning and apply it their daily situations. Similarly, teachers should incorporate the curriculum by narrowing the activities that promote higher order thinking skills. Students' motivation and engagement should enhance to foster learning (Deryakulu, Buyukozturk, Karadeniz & Olkun, 2019).

Teachers who demonstrate high levels of effectiveness in teaching competent students to solve linear equations show different perceived difficulties due to differences in beliefs about effectiveness, and perceived difficulty indicates abandonment. So you may not be convinced that teaching the same topic to your students in a regular classroom would be very effective. Thus, two teachers equally capable of leading a school committee may have different strengths of beliefs about effectiveness, with one believing in their ability and the other believe they are incompetent (Delliger, Bobbett, Olivier & Ellett, 2018)).

In addition, the level of efficiency simply associated to their skills and needs. They need to have a perfect balance being competent and committed in order to grow the best outcomes. This can further more engaged in higher in my work performance that can be achieved only through proper motivation. The teacher will be better motivated when the school head that affect outcomes expectations for professional and personal growth (Tinto, 2005; Kuh, 2001, 2008; Coates, 2007; Krause & Coates, 2008).

Teacher efficacy eventually affects student learning satisfaction and learning outcomes which offered a lot of learning benefits to the educational process to be a successful one, like reducing dropout rate, learning failure falls and the like because an effective teacher is also an effective motivator not only to herself but especially to the learning beneficiaries which are the learners (Deryakulu, Buyukozturk, Karadeniz, & Olkun (2019).

An effective teacher must also be effective model in all aspects especially in values integration. They added that concepts taught in class are entirely useless if the teacher's actions does not conform what he or she has taught in class, thus, to realize the teacher's student engagement a teacher must be cautious enough to become a good implementer because there are learners that are always ready to absorb and replicate what they do whether these are good or bad (Durban & Catalan, 2012).

The second domain of teacher efficacy is on instructional strategies. Teachers' fully understood and engage different strategies to control disruptive behaviors of the in the classroom. Teacher should possess the knowledge of teaching materials and be able to manage the behavior of the students to create consistent instruction to increase student learning through interactive instruction (Crothers & Kolbert, 2008).

Treating co-workers as human beings with respect and dignity and will make them motivated employees who can be more productive and creative. Teachers viewed different strategies and help students to learn and to ensure that learners may achieve and learned yielded fruitful results (Durban and Catalan, 2012).

Motivations are useful ingredients of teachers to engage students in the classrooms. They encourage students to motivate and help individuals to ensure that teaching and learning takes place. Teacher with who believes themselves that they are effective they promote cognitive learning and able to motivate students to engage in developing knowledge and skills and student's desire for learning (Goker, 2009).

Because of the wide range of literature on teaching strategies and the improvement of teaching, the review of literature reflects those studies that describe the use of various instructional strategies in the clinical, classroom, and teaching of strategies. It is from these sources that the Instructional Strategies Inventory was developed. Most of these studies reflect the usefulness of these instructional strategies to education (House, 2005).

The third domain of teacher efficacy is on classroom management. Classroom management technique brings students to engage in the classroom setting. Such behavioral classroom strategies intertwine a classroom atmosphere of students. Students engaged and actively participated in the classroom setting impact on teacher's effectiveness in the field of education (Magableh & Hawamdeh, 2007; Coddling & Smyth, 2008).

Similarly, classroom environment is the way teacher provides the learners with a learning environment that is conducive and free from harm. One of the key factors in classroom management is the content management in which there is a systematized organization of the things inside the classroom, the arrangement of equipment and paraphernalia that will be used in the teaching learning process (Taylor, 2009).

The most viewed problem of teacher is the problem behavior of students in the classroom. They admit that teachers in that situation is lack on classroom management skills and unable to grasp the attention of the students. The positive image of teachers occur when students leads to better performance, which in turn leads to greater efficacy (Darling-Hammond, 2003; Malm & Lofgren, 2006).

D. Correlation between Measures

The roles of relationship and social interaction are vitally important to the power and influence of your support. Social connections and interactions with others involve a network of relationships that surrounds an individual. This interconnected network of influence may include friends, relatives, colleagues, superiors, or professional or personal communities (Cohen & Wills, 1985; House, 1987; House & Wells, 2018).

Social support helps her manage life stressors, mitigate the negative effects of stress, and build mutually beneficial relationships to meet basic psychological needs. Broadly defined as the quality and frequency of interactions with more than one person. The presence of social support helps inspire belief that someone is cared for, valued, and loved. Promotes enhanced self-esteem and a sense of belonging through communication networks and mutual engagement. and reinforce personal values (Cobb, 2016).

Teachers who felt confident or effective in their teaching skills said they felt support from multiple sources. In addition, high self-efficacy allows for greater resilience to difficult professional challenges and stressors (cited in Bandura, 2009) often faced by inexperienced teachers. Knobloch and Whittington (2012) play a leading role in efforts to positively influence teachers' perceptions of situations and reinforce valid beliefs.

Teachers who received positive feedback, support, guidance, and encouragement from students, teachers, administrators, parents, and the community were more efficient in their teaching skills. Especially for prospective teachers, who tend to be more insecure about their skills, their sense of accomplishment and teacher self-efficacy are strongly influenced by the support they perceive as being received or available (Klassen & Chiu, 2010).

Although, there is no lack of research interest in the changes affect teachers' self-efficacy, but there are no data on how spirituality in the workplace changes teachers' beliefs about self-efficacy. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that workplace spirituality plays an important role as one of the main sources of information, namely acquired experience, and may influence teachers' self-efficacy beliefs (Altaf & Awan, 2011).

A spiritual workplace simulates the creativity of a teacher. Creative teachers nurture and develop skills, thus contributing more effectively to educational effectiveness. In this regard, previous research suggests that employees are more creative when they have clear goals (Neck & Milliman, 2016). Another advantage of the spiritual workplace is that communication becomes more credible, allowing individuals to speak up about their spirituality without fear of retribution

(Rutte, 2013). This is mainly because spiritual people have a sense of connection with others and are more aware of their concerns. In summary, the spiritual workplace improves communication with teachers' peers, school leaders, students and their parents, thus influencing teachers' beliefs about self-efficacy and, in turn, job satisfaction. (Adegbola, 2011).

Like many other professionals, teachers need to feel supported in their efforts. Regardless of profession, perceived high levels of support create more effective emotions and make individuals more likely to stay true to their careers. Unfortunately, education has not embraced the corporate world's philosophies regarding onboarding practices for new or early career employees and the allocation of resources for human capital development (Maistre & Pare, 2010).

Relevant references and research provide the most necessary knowledge and background for research subjects, especially the relationships between variables and how these variables and their indicators affect each other. The knowledge gathered by eminent scientists was incorporated in a very comprehensible manner into the formulation of the theoretical framework and the preparation of the questionnaire.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study uses a descriptive correlation design. Descriptive studies describe attitudes and behaviors under investigation, whereas correlation studies involve identifying statistical relationships between two variables (Vanderstoep & Johnston, 2009). Furthermore, the purpose of correlation design is to find the strength of the relationship between the variables under study (Creswell, 2013). In addition, this study builds on the mediation analysis developed by Baron and Kenny (1986) to distinguish and account for procedural factors that primarily influence the strength of associations between social supportive behaviors. I was focused. And by including a third variable, the teacher's sense of effectiveness, we achieve a spiritual workplace. The results of these studies were specific to the situation of public primary schools in Caraga, Eastern Davao. Ranges and samples limit the general applicability of the results. Therefore, common structures may exist, but the results may not be generally applicable to other systems.

Figure 2 is a map of the Philippines highlighting Davao Eastern Province, which consists of 17 regions, with Caraga City, Davao Eastern Province, located in Region XI. Also shown in the figure is a map of the areas where public primary schools are located in Caraga City, prepared by the respondents.

A carefully selected public primary school in the Caraga District, Davao Orient was chosen as the research environment. Range and sample limited the general applicability of the results. Therefore, although there may be common features, the results are not generally applicable to other systems.

The location of the study was Caraga, Davao East. Respondents were 300 public primary schools drawn from 20 public primary schools in the Caraga district. Additionally, the location of the respondents and the location of the survey was Caraga City, Davao State, Eastern Philippines.

The distribution of respondents was as follows.

School A: 50,
School B: 27,
School C: 13,
School D: 32,
School E: 19,
School F: 21,
School G: 29,
School H: 19,
School I: 27,
School J: 29.

A total of 300 respondents will be surveyed. In addition, researchers considered inclusion and exclusion criteria when selecting survey respondents. The interviewed teacher is a regular public primary school teacher from Manai Central District with a Plantilla number listed with the Ministry of Education. Teachers are happy to submit and are given permission by the principal to participate in surveys that are conducted. Teachers who voluntarily consented to informed consent are also included in the survey. Therefore, teachers who clearly acknowledge their disagreement are excluded from the study. All middle school, 11th and 12th graders under the age of 18 were excluded from the study. In addition, researchers will take into account teachers who decided to drop out or drop out during the actual completion of the survey questionnaire.

In this study he used three main research tools. Social support behavior focuses on emotional, instrumental, appreciative, and informational behaviors (Littrell et al. 1994). The Cronbach alpha value for this questionnaire was 0.843, indicating relatively high internal consistency of the items. This questionnaire is a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) with three subscales:

IV. PLANNING, DEVELOPMENT, AND RESULTS

Prior to the conduct of actual survey, the researcher A reliability survey was conducted on a total of 50 respondents. The Cronbach alpha value for this questionnaire was 0.843, indicating relatively high internal consistency of the items.

Part 2 of the first part of the research tool for this study adapted questionnaires from a modified version of Like, Work Place Spiritually, which focused on compassion, mindfulness, meaningful work, and transcendence. (Petchswang & Duchon 2008). The Cronbach alpha value for this questionnaire is 0.761, indicating relatively high internal consistency of the items.

The instruments used in this study were taken from a standardized teacher effectiveness questionnaire with measures such as student engagement, teaching strategies and classroom management (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk-Hoy, 2001). The Cronbach alpha value for this questionnaire

is 0.721, indicating relatively high internal consistency of the items.

Likert scales serve as a basis for describing levels of professional effort. The Likert scale asks you to check a box or leave it blank, depending on a number of items related to attitudes, objects, and stimuli. First, the researcher's advisor created a duly signed application to the Davao Eastern Directorate via Gmail and Google Drive. This allowed the researchers to conduct a survey of different public primary school teachers in the Caraga South district. Davao Oriental Bureau.

In addition, the researchers sent another letter to all school teachers in Caraga South, asking them to conduct a survey. The researchers asked the principal for permission to distribute the questionnaire to each teacher. After the application was approved, an investigation was conducted. Three district teacher educators and one of her former teachers were interviewed and commented on the content and structure. Due to time constraints, the survey was distributed simultaneously to 314 teachers in her 13 schools in San Isidro. The teacher's email address was taken from her school's website. The schools selected are a representative selection of different elementary levels. Each teacher received an email inviting them to participate. The questionnaire was personalized by emailing each participant a link to complete the questionnaire. If teachers did not wish to participate, they were asked to reply to an email stating their reason for not participating, their age, gender, and total teaching experience. One teacher who did not respond or whose actions were only partially completed received an email reminder two weeks later. Of the 303 teachers contacted, 315 participated in the survey. Finally, the researchers counted and tabulated all the data collected from the respondents for statistical analysis. Statistical results were analyzed and interpreted.

The following are the statistical tools that are employed by the Researchers analyzing and interpreting the data:

average and frequency. It is used to determine the teacher's level of professional engagement, metacognitive perception, and quality of professional life for subproblems 1 and 2.

Pearson R. This will be used to examine whether there are significant associations between teachers' professional engagement with subproblem 3, metacognitive awareness, and quality of work life

regression. This helps determine the extent of a teacher's professional involvement, and metacognitive perceptions help shape the quality of professional life.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis and interpretation of the collected data are presented in this part of the work based on the research goals of this study.

The flow of the lecture on the designated theme is as follows.

Degree of social support behavior, degree of social support behavior and degree of spirituality in the workplace, correlation between social support behavior and teacher's sense of competence. The relationship between mental work orientation and perceptions of teacher effectiveness. Effects of Predictor Variables on Teacher's Sense of Effectiveness

Table 1 Degree of social support behavior

Table 1 shows the average values of social support behavior indicators. The overall mean is 4.14 with a standard deviation of 0.33 which is very high. Very high levels are traced back to very high ratings from those surveyed. The reported overall average is the result of calculating the average value for that metric. From the data, we can deduce that the metric with the highest average rating is 4.21, which is very informative. In contrast, the lowest average rating of 4.05 or the highest metric is rating. The two highest metrics are information and sentiment, with average ratings of 4.21 and above and 4.16 and above. Additionally, the top two pieces of information are designed to support teachers in selecting or developing appropriate teaching methods and personalities, and to provide teachers with information on how to change their teaching.

The very high levels of social supportive behavior exhibited by the respondents indicate that teachers have positive self-interpretations such as health and support in school. This finding supports Hamre and Pianta (2006) that positive teacher-student relationships serve as a resource for children at risk of school refusal, while contradictory negative relationships increase that risk.) is consistent with the view of Consistent with Gaytan's 2013 study, these factors help teachers build quality relationships with students and members of the community, leading to increased teacher self-efficacy and teacher retention rates. may improve. Gikas & Grant (2013) provides information, advice, explanations of complex issues, academic support during the learning process and helps teachers provide information on technical techniques to help improve teaching. This was confirmed by a study by Kottler (2010), who found that providing teachers with information about changes in teaching practices was associated with staying up-to-date through equal participation in training courses and seminars and through participation. It is said that information can be obtained through awareness of trends and problems in Students related to them need an information discipline to keep students well informed about the situation in the corporate community.

Table 1: Social Support Behavior

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional	0.48	4.16	High
Instrumental	0.44	4.13	High
Appraisal	0.49	4.05	High
Informational	0.50	4.21	Very High
Overall	0.33	4.14	Very High

A. Level of Work Place Spirituality

The second objective was to measure the level of spirituality in the workplace using a questionnaire with the following indicators:

About compassion, mindfulness, meaningful work, and transcendence. Table 2 presents data on levels of school culture. The calculations show an overall average of over 4.16 with a standard deviation of 0.38, indicating that mentality is always expressed in the workplace. From the data, we can infer that the highest metric with an average score of 4.19 or higher is mindfulness. In contrast, the lowest or still high metric with an average rating of 4.15 is meaningful work. The top two items were mindfulness and compassion, with very high average scores of 4.18 and 4.15 respectively. Moreover, the most important element of mindfulness is working without attention and automatically completing tasks and tasks without being aware of what you are doing. The most important thing for compassion is to be aware of the needs of your colleagues, to be aware of others, and to be compassionate.

Descriptive analysis revealed that teachers had a high level of workplace spirituality. This means that indicators of teachers' spirituality in the workplace (compassion, mindfulness, meaningful work, and transcendence) were almost always evident. This finding is supported by lecturers Zerach & Levin (2018), who said workplace spirituality teachers know how to embrace general diversity, from ideas to emotional perspectives. . Only with spiritual maturity do we have the opportunity to replace the comfort of being with reason, massage postures, and a sense of priority for function and organization.

Moreover, the spirituality of people and teachers evolves over time and is influenced by meaningful relationships with others through lived experience (Ambrose, 2005). When the concept of spirituality is discussed in the school context, there are various ways to interpret it at the individual, group-centered, and faith-based level, followed by secular concerns in school (Klerk, 2014).).

Table 2: Work Place Spirituality

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Compassion	0.60	4.18	High
Mindfulness	0.49	4.19	High
Meaningful Work	0.46	4.15	High
Transcendence	0.44	4.16	High
Overall	0.38	4.17	High

B. Level of Professional Commitment

Level of Teachers' Sense of Efficacy The third objective was to determine the level of teachers' sense of efficacy which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of teachers' sense of efficacy. Computations yield a grand mean of 4.11 or high with a standard deviation of 0.31 and this indicates that the teachers' sense of efficacy is always manifested. It could be gleaned from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.11 or high is efficacy in instructional strategies. In

contrast, indicator with the lowest mean rating of 4.11 or still high is efficacy of student engagement.

The two most important points are the effectiveness of teaching strategies and the effectiveness of classroom management. In addition, developing alternative strategies in the classroom and extending alternative explanations, such as when students are confused, is also an important point of teaching strategy effectiveness. Controlling disruptive behavior in the classroom and establishing routines to keep activities running smoothly are key to effective classroom management.

Table 3: Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Efficacy in Student Engagement	0.46	4.05	High
Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	0.47	4.17	High
Efficacy in Classroom Management	0.31	4.11	High
Overall	0.31	4.11	High

C. Significance of the Relationship between Social Support Behavior and Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

Table 4 presents the results of a test examining the relationship between social support behavior and teacher perceptions of effectiveness. This relationship was tested at the 0.05 significance level. In particular, significant positive associations were found between all measures of social support behavior and teachers' sense of effectiveness, as indicated by p-values less than 0.05.

instrumental Except behavior they are significant. Not significant because it is below the significance level.

If sentiment correlates with the overall measure of perceptions of teacher effectiveness, this is not significant with an r-value of 0.034 and a rank value of p=561, below the significance level of 0.05 specified in this study. If the ratings were correlated with the overall measure of teacher effectiveness, the sense of effectiveness was significant with an r-value of 0.0177 and a rank value of p=044, which is below the significance level of 0.05, thus suggesting that the teaching All but strategy and teaching strategies matter. Effectiveness of classroom management,

If all measures of social support behavior correlated with measures of teacher competence and all R-values were greater than p<0.05, i.e. at a significant level, emotional and

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the and Social Support Behavior and Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

Social Support Behavior	Teachers' Sense of Efficacy			
	Efficacy in Student Engagement	Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	Efficacy in Classroom Management	Overall
Emotional	.017 (0.771)	-.035 (0.543)	.132* (0.023)	.034 (0.561)
Instrumental	.068 (0.242)	-.034 (0.555)	.004 (0.948)	.017 (0.770)
Appraisal	.150* (0.009)	.042 (0.470)	.071 (0.218)	.117* (0.044)
Informational	.214* (0.000)	.247* (0.000)	.191* (0.001)	.290* (0.000)
Overall	.167* (0.004)	.086 (0.139)	.149* (0.010)	.173* (0.003)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

This study shows that there is a significant correlation between social supportive behavior and teacher's sense of effectiveness. This means that social support behavior influences the sense of effectiveness that is evident from the

data. This confirms research by House and Wells (2018) that found that social interactions are important in underpinning power and influence. Social connections and interactions with others involve the network of relationships that

surrounds us. This interconnected network of influence may include friends, relatives, co-workers, superiors, or professional or personal communities.

These findings support Cobb (2016), who states that teachers' social support helps instill the belief that someone is cared for, valued, and loved. Promotes enhanced self-esteem and a sense of belonging through communication networks and mutual engagement. and reinforce personal values

D. Relationship between Work Place Spiritually and Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

Table 5 shows the results of testing the relationship between workplace mental engagement and teacher's sense of effectiveness. As a result, overall scores indicate a positive and significant association between workplace mental engagement and teachers' sense of effectiveness. With an overall r-value of 0.510 and a p-value of $p < 1$, the overall score reflects that mentally workplaces are positively correlated with perceived teacher effectiveness. 0.01, so we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between the two variables.

If caring is correlated with the teacher's sense of overall effectiveness, the r value is 0.260 and the rank value is $p < 1$. 0.01 is less than 0.05. Therefore, the importance established

in this study is significant, except for the effectiveness of classroom management.

If mindfulness correlates with a teacher's sense of overall effectiveness, the r-value is 0.273 and the rank value is $p < 1$. 0.01 is less than the 0.05 significance level specified in this study, so it is significant except for classroom effectiveness.

Testing for the relationship between workplace mental attitudes and teachers' perceptions of effectiveness revealed an important relationship between workplace mental attitudes and teachers' perceptions of effectiveness. I was. This means that the teacher's mental workplace simulates the teacher's creativity. Creative teachers nurture and develop skills, thus contributing more effectively to educational effectiveness. In this regard, previous research suggests that employees are more creative when they have clear goals (Neck & Milliman, 2016).

Additionally, Adegbola (2011) hypothesized that spiritual persons have a sense of connection with others and are more aware of their concerns. In summary, the spiritual workplace improves teacher communication with peers, school leaders, students and their parents, thus influencing teachers' beliefs about self-efficacy and, in turn, job satisfaction. .

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between Work Place Spiritually and Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

Work Place Spiritually	Teachers' Sense of Efficacy			
	Efficacy in Student Engagement	Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	Efficacy in Classroom Management	Overall
Compassion	.276* (0.000)	.217* (0.000)	.050 (0.384)	.260* (0.000)
Mindfulness	.254* (0.000)	.248* (0.000)	.075 (0.199)	.273* (0.000)
Meaningful Work	.243* (0.000)	.391* (0.000)	.224* (0.000)	.387* (0.000)
Transcendence	.495* (0.000)	.619* (0.000)	.398* (0.000)	.680* (0.000)
Overall	.413* (0.000)	.469* (0.000)	.229* (0.000)	.510* (0.000)

E. The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Teachers' Sense of Efficacy

The data shown in Table 6 are the regression coefficients used to test for significance.

Effects of global social supportive behaviors and mental activities in the workplace on teachers' sense of effectiveness. Data using regression analysis showed that general social support behaviors and mental workplaces significantly influenced teachers' sense of effectiveness. The F-value was 58.778, $p < 0.01$. This means that social support behavior and workplace have a significant impact on perceptions of teacher effectiveness spiritually, as the probability value $p < 0.01$. An R2 value of 0.284 indicates that 28.4 percent of the differences in workplace social support behavior and spiritual engagement are due to differences in teachers' perceptions of effectiveness, with the

remaining 71.6 percent due to other factors identified in the study. means to be covered.

However, social support behavior, with the highest beta coefficient of 0.587, was found to be a significant predictor of teacher achievement. The importance of variable effects on perceptions of teacher effectiveness showed that social supportive behaviors were associated with indicators such as emotional, instrumental, evaluative, and informational. On the other hand, teacher competence is a good indicator of mental performance in the workplace, especially with indicators such as compassion, mindfulness, meaningful work, and transcendence.

Clearly, this result supports the conceptual analysis of Brouwers and Tomic (2000), who state that spirituality involves the concept of inner life guided by conscience. This expansion of our inner life positively shapes other aspects of our lives, such as our attitudes, beliefs, and actions. As mentioned earlier, self-efficacy is an assessment of an individual's ability to achieve desired outcomes. People with high self-efficacy persevere and remain confident in the face of difficult challenges. At the same time, this study

corroborates the findings of Maistre and Pare, 2010), who stated that perceived high levels of support produced more effective emotions and made individuals more likely to remain loyal to their careers. I'm here. Unfortunately, the educational setting has not embraced the corporate world philosophy regarding the onboarding practices of new and junior employees and the allocation of resources for human capital development.

Table 6: The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Professional Commitment

Professional Commitment (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	-.938	.301	-3.113	.002
Metacognitive Awareness (MA)	.290	.360	6.381	.000
Quality of Work Life (QWL)	.536	.898	11.809	.000
R	.715			
R ²	.511			
F	155.34			
p	.000			

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Several recommendations are made based on the above findings and conclusions. Due to the very high level of metacognitive awareness, it is recommended that future teachers take courses focused on enhancing their metacognitive awareness. This is because if these teacher candidates utilize their metacognitive perceptions during their school years, it will be natural for them to be proactive in implementing strategies in the classroom. Additionally, school leaders have consistent, effective and applicable in-service learning opportunities to improve teaching skills, enabling all teachers to acquire and develop the skills they need. This important relationship urges policy makers, especially education ministry officials, to primarily improve teachers' metacognition, if existing education policies meet the needs and challenges of his 21st century educator. and recommended a review and rethinking with a focus on improving teacher engagement. teachers. Finally, future research investigating other variables that may influence metacognitive awareness and will be of most importance to the research community should be considered.

On the one hand, it recommends that by achieving job satisfaction, it is possible to improve the quality of work life more efficiently and effectively, which in turn ensures the successful formation of a student community. will be At the same time, work-life balance also helps teachers balance professional accomplishments with personal commitments and family concerns. In the current study, researchers investigated a variety of factors that have a significant impact on work-life balance status. Finally, this research study could serve as a starting point for similar studies in different settings.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, within limits and limitations (questionnaire, number of participants, etc.), several conclusions can be drawn.

The level of social support behavior is high. On the other hand, workplace morale is also very high. Awareness of teacher performance is at a high level.

Moreover, there is a significant association between social supportive behavior and teachers' perceived effectiveness. This result is consistent with the work of Klassen & Chiu (2010). The study states that teachers who receive positive feedback, support, guidance, and encouragement from students, teachers, administrators, parents, and the community are more effective in their teaching skills. Also, psychologically, attitudes in the workplace are highly correlated with feelings about teacher effectiveness. This result is consistent with her Rutte (2013), who stated that spiritual people have a sense of connection with others and are more aware of their concerns. In summary, the spiritual workplace improves communication with teachers' peers, school leaders, students and their parents, which in turn affects teachers' self-efficacy. Recommendation.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, a number of recommendations are offered. Since there is a high level of social support behavior, very high level of workplace spiritually of and high level of self-efficacy, thereby enhance teacher classroom effectiveness that will help achieve student outcomes. They could also develop and implement teaching programs designed to bridge educational gaps to address the needs of teachers specifically on the identified teachers' strengths and needs. Provide opportunities for school

administrators and teacher educators to integrate best practices in mentoring and induction programs. In an effort to increase student achievement, improve job satisfaction, and enhance career commitment for novice teachers, school administrators should devote more time and resources to the development of teacher self-efficacy.

The Department of Education may conduct additional training and seminars to help teachers and students improve social support behaviors and increase self-efficacy so that students can actively participate. The magnitude of this effect suggests that students need to enhance their perception of social support in order to achieve better student engagement outcomes. Finally, future research to examine other variables that may mediate the relationship between student participation and self-efficacy should be considered, which will be of paramount importance to the research community. . Researchers need to explore differences between each group of educators in terms of years of teaching experience and status of teacher development relationships with other teachers. To increase teacher self-efficacy, it is important for teacher educators, school administrators and educational professionals to establish specific practices to increase teachers' awareness of available support.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] Aboobaker, N., Edward, M., & KA, Z. (2020). Workplace spirituality and employee loyalty: an empirical investigation among millennials in India. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 14(2), 211-225.
- [2.] Adnan, N., Bhatti, O. K., & Farooq, W. (2020). Relating ethical leadership with work engagement: How workplace spirituality mediates?. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1739494.
- [3.] Arokiasamy, A., & Tat, H. (2020). Exploring the influence of transformational leadership on work engagement and workplace spirituality of academic employees in the private higher education institutions in Malaysia. *Management Science Letters*, 10(4), 855-864.
- [4.] Bantha, T., & Nayak, U. (2020). The relation of workplace spirituality with employees' innovative work behaviour: the mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, 13(2), 223-235.
- [5.] Bharadwaj, S. H. U. B. H. A. N. G. I., & Jamal, T. (2020). In Search of Spiritual Workplaces: An Empirical Evidence Of Workplace Spirituality And Employee Performance In The Indian IT Industry. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(3), 1116-1124.
- [6.] De Carlo, A., Dal Corso, L., Carluccio, F., Colledani, D., & Falco, A. (2020). Positive supervisor behaviors and employee performance: The serial mediation of workplace spirituality and work engagement. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 1834.
- [7.] Dubey, P., Pathak, A. K., & Sahu, K. K. (2020). Correlates of workplace spirituality on job satisfaction, leadership, organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational growth: A literature-based study from organisational perspective. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4), 1493-1502.
- [8.] Exner-Cortens, D., Wright, A., Claussen, C., & Truscott, E. (2021). A systematic review of adolescent masculinities and associations with internalizing behavior problems and social support. *American journal of community psychology*, 68(1-2), 215-231.

- [9.] Félix, S., de Lourdes, M., Ribeiro, I., Cunha, B., Ramalho, S., Vaz, A. R., & Conceição, E. (2021). A preliminary study on the psychosocial impact of COVID-19 lockdown in post-bariatric surgery women: the importance of eating behavior, health care access, and social support. *Current Psychology*, 40(12), 6275-6281.
- [10.] Garg, N. (2020). Promoting organizational performance in Indian insurance industry: The roles of workplace spirituality and organizational citizenship behaviour. *Global Business Review*, 21(3), 834-849.
- [11.] Goddard, R. D., Bailes, L. P., & Kim, M. (2021). Principal efficacy beliefs for instructional leadership and their relation to teachers' sense of collective efficacy and student achievement. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 20(3), 472-493.
- [12.] Hamm, J. V., Lambert, K., Little, T. D., Farmer, T. W., & Harris, M. V. (2021). A longitudinal study of interdisciplinary team relational supports of sixth-grade teachers' sense of efficacy and perceived collective efficacy of team members. *The Elementary School Journal*, 122(2), 141-164.
- [13.] Hwang, J., Yoo, Y., & Kim, I. (2021). Dysfunctional customer behavior, employee service sabotage, and sustainability: can social support make a difference?. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(7), 3628.
- [14.] Iqbal, M., Adawiyah, W. R., Suroso, A., & Wihuda, F. (2020). Exploring the impact of workplace spirituality on nurse work engagement: an empirical study on Indonesian government hospitals. *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*, 36(3), 351-369.
- [15.] Jolly, P. M., Kong, D. T., & Kim, K. Y. (2021). Social support at work: An integrative review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 42(2), 229-251.
- [16.] Labrague, L. J. (2021). Psychological resilience, coping behaviours and social support among health care workers during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review of quantitative studies. *Journal of nursing management*, 29(7), 1893-1905.
- [17.] Lata, M., & Chaudhary, R. (2020). Dark Triad and instigated incivility: The moderating role of workplace spirituality. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 166, 110090.
- [18.] Li, J., Yao, M., & Liu, H. (2021). From social support to adolescents' subjective well-being: The mediating role of emotion regulation and prosocial behavior and gender difference. *Child Indicators Research*, 14, 77-93.
- [19.] Lin, X., & Kishore, R. (2021). Social media-enabled healthcare: a conceptual model of social media affordances, online social support, and health behaviors and outcomes. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 166, 120574.
- [20.] Liu, A., Wang, W., & Wu, X. (2021). Self-compassion and posttraumatic growth mediate the relations between social support, prosocial behavior, and antisocial behavior among adolescents after the Ya'an earthquake. *European journal of psychotraumatology*, 12(1), 1864949.
- [21.] Matvienko-Sikar, K., Pope, J., Cremin, A., Carr, H., Leitao, S., Olander, E. K., & Meaney, S. (2021). Differences in levels of stress, social support, health behaviours, and stress-reduction strategies for women pregnant before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, and based on phases of pandemic restrictions, in Ireland. *Women and Birth*, 34(5), 447-454.
- [22.] Meshi, D., & Ellithorpe, M. E. (2021). Problematic social media use and social support received in real-life versus on social media: Associations with depression, anxiety and social isolation. *Addictive Behaviors*, 119, 106949.
- [23.] Mitchell, K. J., Banyard, V., Goodman, K. L., Strøm, I. F., & Ybarra, M. L. (2021). Exposure to suicidal behavior and social support among sexual-and gender-minority youth. *Pediatrics*, 147(4).
- [24.] Moore, S. E., Wierenga, K. L., Prince, D. M., Gillani, B., & Mintz, L. J. (2021). Disproportionate impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on perceived social support, mental health and somatic symptoms in sexual and gender minority populations. *Journal of homosexuality*, 68(4), 577-591.
- [25.] Otaeye-Ebede, L., Shaffakat, S., & Foster, S. (2020). A multilevel model examining the relationships between workplace spirituality, ethical climate and outcomes: A social cognitive theory perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 166(3), 611-626.
- [26.] Paul, M., Jena, L. K., & Sahoo, K. (2020). Workplace spirituality and workforce agility: a psychological exploration among teaching professionals. *Journal of religion and health*, 59(1), 135-153.
- [27.] Pintus, A., Bertolini, C., Scipione, L., & Antonietti, M. (2021). Validity and reliability of the Italian version of the Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(6), 1166-1175.
- [28.] Rathee, R., & Rajain, P. (2020). Workplace spirituality: A comparative study of various models. *Jindal Journal of Business Research*, 9(1), 27-40.
- [29.] Salas-Rodríguez, F., Lara, S., & Martínez, M. (2021). Spanish version of the Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale: An adaptation and validation study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 714145.
- [30.] Sharma, P. K., & Kumra, R. (2020). Relationship between workplace spirituality, organizational justice and mental health: mediation role of employee engagement. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 17(5), 627-650.
- [31.] Wentzel, K. R., Muenks, K., McNeish, D., & Russell, S. (2018). Emotional support, social goals, and classroom behavior: A multilevel, multisite study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(5), 611-627. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000239>
- [32.] Won, M. R., Choi, E. J., Ko, E., Um, Y. J., & Choi, Y. J. (2021). The mediating effect of life satisfaction and the moderated mediating effect of social support on the relationship between depression and suicidal behavior among older adults. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*, 36(11), 1732-1738.

- [33.] Yang, X. (2021). Exchanging social support in social commerce: The role of peer relations. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 124, 106911.
- [34.] Ye, Y., Huang, X., & Liu, Y. (2021). Social support and academic burnout among university students: a moderated mediation model. *Psychology research and behavior management*, 335-344.
- [35.] Zhang, S. (2020). Workplace spirituality and unethical pro-organizational behavior: The mediating effect of job satisfaction. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 161, 687-705.
- [36.] Zheng, X., Wang, Z., Chen, H., & Xie, F. (2021). The relationship between self-esteem and internet altruistic behavior: The mediating effect of online social support and its gender differences. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 172, 110588.
- [37.] Zhang, Q., Huang, F., Zhang, L., Li, S., & Zhang, J. (2021). The effect of high blood pressure-health literacy, self-management behavior, self-efficacy and social support on the health-related quality of life of Kazakh hypertension patients in a low-income rural area of China: a structural equation model. *BMC public health*, 21(1), 1-10.
- [38.] Zou, W. C., Houghton, J. D., & Li, J. J. (2020). Workplace spirituality as a means of enhancing service employee well-being through emotional labor strategy choice. *Current Psychology*, 1-16.